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*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D7.2 Data Management Plan

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FIERCE consortium

#	Participant	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
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2	BEN	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU	DK
3	BEN	SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE	SNS	IT
4	BEN	UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID	UCM	ES
5	BEN	SMART VENICE SRL	SV	IT
6	BEN	ALTERNATIVES EUROPEENNES ASSOCIATION	EA	FR
7	BEN	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	PL
8	BEN	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	EL
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
EA	Ethics Advisor
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association
ORD	Open Research Data
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the initial version of the Data Management Plan, which is directly connected with the work performed under Task 7.1 - "Project Coordination and Management", in the context of WP7 – "Project Management and Coordination". It serves as the initial plan for the collection, organization, storing and sharing of the knowledge and data created within the project. The described data management plan is formulated based on several inputs, namely: a) the FIERCE Description of Action (DOA) document, b) the European Commission guidelines for data management of H2020/HE research projects and c) the input from the project consortium members.

The document reflects the appropriate methodologies adopted and the tools and repositories utilised for data management and disseminating all available information generated by the FIERCE project.

1. Introduction to the FIERCE Project

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender actors and discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2021. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, will be studied through frame analysis, political ethnography and Social Network Analysis on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. FIERCE will cover eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE moves beyond a country-based approach and provides a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics and output of the policy process. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. Description of WP7 – Project Management & Coordination

The main objectives of this Work Package include:

- Coordination of decision making and conflict resolution;
- Handling the administrative and financial management of the project;
- Coordination of the Project and Scientific management;
- Implementing quality, innovation, and risk management procedures, and consideration of ethical and legal matters during the project implementation.

1.3. Introduction to the deliverable report – Document Scope

The purpose of this deliverable report is to provide a comprehensive data management plan for the FIERCE project. The data management plan outlines the procedures and strategies for handling the data generated during the project's lifecycle, from collection to preservation and sharing. This data management plan will provide a framework for managing the research data generated during the project. It is intended to ensure the integrity, availability, and long-term preservation of the data, as well as to facilitate data sharing and reuse.

1.4. Document Structure

This document is comprised of the following chapters: **Chapter 1** introduces the project and describes the scope of the document. It includes a summary of the project, as well as a description of the project's management and coordination. **Chapter 2** outlines the methodological framework for the data management plan, including the DMP process, responsibilities, and decision-making. It also covers data security, GDPR compliance, project research datasets, and project publications. **Chapter 3** provides

guidelines and procedures for data protection, including steps prior to data collection, methodologies for anonymization and pseudonymization, and management and custody of collected data. **Chapter 4** discusses ethical treatment, including the project work break structure and proactive approach. **Chapter 5** covers ethics approvals per partner. Finally, **Chapter 6** summarizes the report's findings and conclusions. Two annexes are included, which provide FAIR templates for the project. The report concludes with a reference section listing all the sources used in the document.

2. Methodological Framework for Data Management Plan

The role of a DMP is to define the framework for the handling of research data generated or acquired as the project progresses but also after its completion. Subjects for investigation include: the nature of the data in question, which data will be collected and to whom they will be useful, the use of metadata to render data easily retrievable, standardization, whether and which data will be open-access, how they will be stored and preserved etc.

The FIERCE DMP complies with the FAIR Principles: The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles provide a framework for managing research data in a way that maximizes its potential for reuse, thereby promoting the transparency, reproducibility, and impact of scientific research. In Horizon Europe, the European Union's research and innovation funding programme, FAIR data management is a crucial aspect for ensuring the success and impact of research projects.

By adopting the FAIR principles in data management from the outset, making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, ensuring data quality, and engaging with the research community, researchers can maximize the potential impact of their research and contribute to the transparency and reproducibility of scientific research.

The components included in FAIR are the following:

- **Data Summary;**

A data summary for FAIR principles would provide a brief overview of the key concepts and guidelines of FAIR data management. This could include a description of the four key principles of FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), as well as practical guidance on how to implement FAIR data practices in research projects. The summary might also include information on the benefits of FAIR data, such as increased efficiency, reproducibility, and transparency in research. Additionally, it could outline any relevant policies or regulations related to FAIR data management, as well as resources or tools available to help researchers implement FAIR practices in their work.

- **FAIR Data Principles¹;**

1. Plan for FAIR data management from the outset: FAIR data management should be integrated into the project planning phase, and researchers should plan how to make their data FAIR from the beginning of the project. This includes establishing data management plans, identifying data standards, and selecting appropriate repositories for data storage. (European Commission, 2021)
2. Make the data findable: To make data findable, metadata should be used that includes information on the data's creators, date of creation, and the context of the data. The metadata should be machine-readable, using standard vocabularies and formats to enhance interoperability. (Wilkinson et al., 2016)
3. Make the data accessible: To make data accessible, it should be stored in a trusted repository that provides open access to the data. The repository should provide persistent identifiers, such as DOIs or URIs, to ensure the data's long-term accessibility and allow others to cite and reuse the data. (Recker & Bubke, 2020)

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020:
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

4. **Make the data interoperable:** To make data interoperable, standard formats and vocabularies should be used to enable data to be easily combined and reused. This includes providing clear documentation on the data structure, format, and semantics to ensure that the data is understandable to others. (Wilkinson et al., 2016)
 5. **Make the data reusable:** To make data reusable, it should be licensed in a way that permits reuse and any restrictions on the data use should be clearly stated. Documentation on how the data was collected and processed should be provided to allow others to reproduce and build upon the research. (Federer, 2018)
 6. **Ensure data quality:** To ensure data quality, quality control procedures should be established to verify data accuracy, completeness and consistency. Any data processing steps taken should also be documented to ensure that the data can be audited and replicated. (Kratz & Strasser, 2015)
 7. **Engage with the research community:** To promote the adoption of FAIR data management practices, researchers should engage with the research community and disseminate information on FAIR data management principles and practices. This includes sharing data management plans, data and tools through open access repositories and collaborating with other researchers and stakeholders to establish best practices. (European Commission, 2021)
- **Allocation of resources;**
 - **Data Security;**

As a Horizon Europe project, it is essential to ensure the security of the data generated during the research project. The project team will implement appropriate security measures to protect the confidentiality, integrity and availability of the data. The following outlines the security measures that will be put in place for this project.

1. **Access Control:** Access to the data will be restricted to authorized personnel only. A secure password-protected system will be put in place, and access to the data will be granted on a need-to-know basis. Access controls will be set up to prevent unauthorized access, and data will only be shared with individuals or organizations that have signed a data sharing agreement.
2. **Data Encryption:** Data encryption is an essential security measure that protects data from unauthorized access. Data will be encrypted when transmitted over the network, stored on external devices or cloud-based storage, and when transferred between team members.
3. **Data Backup:** Regular data backups will be performed to protect against data loss due to technical failures or other incidents. Backups will be stored in secure locations that are separate from the original data storage.
4. **Data Retention:** The project team will follow the data retention policy outlined in this plan. The retention policy will specify how long the data will be kept and when it will be destroyed. Data will be kept for as long as required to support the research or as required by law or funding agency regulations.
5. **Data Destruction:** When data is no longer required, it will be destroyed securely. This includes ensuring that no residual data remains on devices or media that are being disposed of or repurposed. Data destruction will follow the guidelines and procedures outlined in the data retention policy.

6. **Training:** Project team members will receive training on data security policies and procedures, including how to recognize potential security risks and how to respond to security incidents.
7. **Horizon Europe Guidelines:** The project team will ensure that all data security measures are in compliance with the Horizon Europe guidelines on data security and management.

In conclusion, the security measures outlined in this plan will protect the data generated during the Horizon Europe project from unauthorized access, alteration, or loss. By implementing these security measures, we will ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the data throughout the project's lifecycle and ensure that the data complies with the Horizon Europe guidelines on data security and management.

- **Ethical Aspects;**

Ethical considerations are an essential aspect of ensuring that research data is managed in a way that is consistent with the FAIR principles.

The ethical aspects of the FAIR principles are particularly relevant to the "A" in FAIR, which stands for "Accessible." Making data accessible to others may raise ethical concerns regarding privacy, confidentiality, and data protection. Researchers must ensure that the data they share is free of personal identifiers and other sensitive information that could be used to identify individuals or violate their privacy rights.

Additionally, researchers must consider the ethical implications of sharing data that was collected from vulnerable populations, such as children or individuals with disabilities. In such cases, researchers must take appropriate measures to ensure that the data is anonymized and that the privacy and rights of the research subjects are protected.

The ethical aspects of the FAIR principles also include considerations related to the ownership and intellectual property rights of the data. Researchers must ensure that they have the necessary permissions and licenses to share data and that any restrictions on the use of the data are clearly stated.

In summary, ethical considerations are an essential aspect of the FAIR principles, particularly in ensuring that research data is made accessible in a way that protects the privacy and rights of research subjects and respects intellectual property rights. By adhering to the ethical aspects of the FAIR principles, researchers can promote the transparency, reproducibility, and impact of their research while maintaining the highest standards of ethical conduct.

- **Other Issues ;**

The Data Summary and the FAIR Data Principles will be addressed separately for each dataset that is expected to be generated from the FIERCE project. In the adapted template, for the sake of readability, all questions under Data Summary and FAIR Data Principles were codified and transformed in a bullet list. This template will be used for all dataset descriptions. In this early stage, it is not required to cover exhaustively all points for each dataset, as this DMP will be updated during the project, whenever new data or other significant changes emerge.

No requirement is set, within the ambit of the project, for allocation of resources for storage and archiving, as the selected online storage solutions described below are available free of charge.

As regards publication and other open access costs, they will be provided under the project².

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/oa-pilot/h2020-hi-erc-oa-guide_en.pdf

By default, Horizon 2020 projects participate in the Open Research Data Pilot.

The Open Research Data Pilot is an initiative launched by the European Commission that aims to promote the open sharing and reuse of research data generated by EU-funded research projects (European Commission, 2016).

The Open Research Data Pilot requires that all research data produced in a project be made openly available for access, sharing, and reuse, except where there are legal or ethical reasons for restricting access to the data. This means that data must be stored in a trusted repository, such as Zenodo or Figshare, and be assigned a persistent identifier, such as a DOI or URI, to ensure its long-term accessibility (European Commission, 2016).

Project Partners must also provide open access, through the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The purpose of the bibliographic metadata requirement is to make it easier to find publications and ensure that EU funding is acknowledged. Information on EU funding must therefore be included as part of bibliographic metadata so that Horizon 2020 can be properly monitored, statistics produced, and the programme's impact assessed.

All participating partners are required to ensure open access for their peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results, as defined in Article 17 of the Horizon Europe- General MGA³.

There are two main routes to open access for scientific publications in Horizon Europe⁴:

1. **Green Open Access:** This route allows researchers to self-archive their final peer-reviewed manuscript or the final published version of the article in a repository. The repository must be open access and enable free access to the publication. The embargo period for the final published version is 6 months in most cases, although this can be extended to 12 months for certain disciplines.
2. **Gold Open Access:** This route involves publishing the article in an open access journal that provides immediate and unrestricted access to the publication. The journal must be listed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) or follow the Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association (OASPA) criteria for open access publishing.

Both routes require compliance with the Horizon Europe Open Access policy, which sets out specific requirements for the metadata and licensing of publications, as well as reporting on open access compliance. Additionally, research data resulting from Horizon Europe-funded research must also be made openly accessible, either through a repository or by other means.

Therefore, the open access to publications process is as follows:

³ Horizon Europe Multi-Beneficiary General Model Grant Agreement v1.1-April 2022, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/agr-contr/general-mga_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

⁴ European Commission. (2021). Open Access in Horizon Europe. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/dissemination-and-exploitation-research-results_en, OpenAIRE. (2021). Horizon Europe Open Access requirements: Green and Gold routes. <https://www.openaire.eu/horizon-europe-open-access-requirements-green-and-gold-routes>, Science Europe. (2021). Plan S and Horizon Europe. <https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/plan-s-and-horizon-europe/>, and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). (2020). Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/0c15f98a-5d68-11e8-ab9c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>

1. Publications are deposited in online repositories.
2. Open access route is selected.
3. Open access is granted to publications.

Note that the steps mentioned above are not strictly successive, but may occur simultaneously, depending on the selected open-access route and a possible embargo period set by the consortium.

Regarding research data for projects participating in the ORD (Open research Data) pilot, it is obligatory to ensure open-access to all data needed for result validation⁵. Whether other parts of data will be made open-access, is left to the discretion of the beneficiaries, as they must ensure that the main objective of the project will not be jeopardised by the publicity. Ethical and privacy concerns raised by publication of particular data, as well as protection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are also a great deterrent to granting open access.

The open-access research data must be deposited in online repositories, available for access, mining, exploiting, processing and disseminating, free of charge for any user, accompanied by the appropriate information — via the repository — regarding the specific tools and instruments that beneficiaries have at their disposal, considered to be necessary for validating the results. Where possible, these tools or instruments should be provided.

The above-described procedures are summarised in the following diagram:

Figure 1 - Granting Open Access Diagram

Provision for GDPR⁶ compliance is also included, as described in the GDPR compliance section of the FIERCE DMP.

Organisations acquiring and/or processing data of natural persons are required to adopt more robust data management and security systems. At the same time GDPR empowers citizens, by enhancing monitoring and control over their own data. As stated in the Regulation (Article 1):

⁵ Article 29.3, H2020 Multi-Beneficiary General Model Grant Agreement

⁶ General Data Protection Regulation, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

- (i) the Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data.
- (ii) the Regulation protects fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and in particular their right to the protection of personal data.
- (iii) The free movement of personal data within the Union shall be neither restricted nor prohibited for reasons connected with the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data.

For further details on GDPR please see deliverables reports of WP7 and WP8.

As previously noted, significant changes on data, which may arise in the course of the project are to be reported in the form of new versions of the present deliverable. Finally, all generated and collected project data will be described in detail in M24 and D7.4 and at the end of the project in the Final Report (M36).

2.1. DMP Process

The FIERCE DMP Process is a set of steps aiming to classify the various datasets according to the analysis presented in the previous section. Each step of the process contains a question requiring a reply. The reply given in each step defines the actual status, and the respective handling, for each dataset generated or acquired during the project. Data storage, preservation and sharing were intentionally not included in the questionnaire, as all the datasets produced and used in the FIERCE project will be stored, preserved and shared through the selected platforms (section 3), and thus, these aspects of data management are common for all datasets.

For the FIERCE project, the following questions were selected to classify the datasets:

Table 1 The Data Management Process approach for each dataset.

Issues to be addressed for dataset	Positive Answer (yes)	Negative Answer (no)
Needed for result validation?	Public	Private
Produces added value to third parties?	Public	Private
Can the created data - which may be derived from third-party data - be shared?	Public	Private
Contains personal data as referred to in GDPR - Article 4?	Private	Public
Contains data back traceable to private individuals?	Private	Public
Contains data that could be used in activities raising ethical issues or constitute a danger to the society?	Private	Public
Contains sensitive data or a security threat for one or more partners of the project (e.g. confidential information)?	Private	Public

Either a Licence restriction or an embargo is applied?	Private	Public
Contains data jeopardising a project patent?	Private	Public

2.2. Responsibilities and Decision Making

All involved partners in the FIERCE project are solely responsible for the own data they create and upload. Such data is not accessible to other organisations or individuals without prior permission. The decision of what data to store, how to process them and to whom they will permit access and under what conditions, befalls that organisation. Since the collection of mostly personal data within FIERCE coincides with the same data collection in the day-to-day operations of the pilot organisations, the responsibility cannot and should not be transferred to other parties.

Within this framework, the consortium as a whole will be permitted access to aggregated and anonymised data from the repositories of the pilot partners for research and dissemination purposes. The data that will be allowed to be used, the type and the extent of the anonymisation and aggregation algorithms that will be used will need to be approved by the organisations that will provide the data. A final approval for the dissemination of the aggregated and anonymised data from the pilot operation and for any use will be provided by the Innovation/Scientific Manager and the Technical Manager of the project.

2.3. Data Security and GDPR Compliance

The data subjects and overall GDPR framework are presented in D7.1 “Project Handbook and Management”, D7.3 “Ethics requirement for check”, and D8.1” Ethics Requirement No.1”. In these deliverables, an analytical description of how the FIERCE project implements the GDPR is included, along with the data subjects involved in the pilot cases, the types and sources of data (including personal data) that will be collected and processed, the data controllers, the data processors, the processing activities of the personal data that are taking place in the FIERCE project, and how the rights of all relevant stakeholders will be protected.

According to Article 4 of the EU GDPR, the Data Controller, the Data Processor and the Data Recipient are defined as follows:

Controller – “means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data”.

Processor – “means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller”.

Recipient – “means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not”.

2.4. Project Research Datasets

This chapter is about the datasets that are/ will be extracted from FIERCE and will be used for academic research purposes. Regarding the results from the pilot operation, any anonymised and/or aggregated datasets that may become available outside the consortium will follow the approval procedure described above and will be formed in a manner that will make them potentially useful without allowing any personal identification of specific cases.

In this chapter, these data sets will be reported as they become available using the relevant FAIR analysis table.

Table 2 Name of Research Data set

1. Data summary	
Purpose	
Relation to the objectives of the project	
Types/Formats	
Re-use of any existing data	
Origin	
Size	
Utility for others	
2. FAIR Data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
Metadata provision	
Metadata standards	
Unique identifier	
Naming conventions	
Search keywords	
Version control	
2.2 Making data openly Accessible	
Classification	
Sharing and access regimes	
Needed method/software	
Repository	
Access authorisation	
2.3. Making data interoperable	
Data/metadata vocabularies and other I/O standards	
Mapping to common ontologies	
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	

Licence	
Re-use availability schedule	
Re-use by third parties	
Quality assurance	
Availability period	

2.5. Project Publications

2.5.1. Scientific Publications

Along with the dissemination of project deliverables and datasets, we are considering as part of the DMP, further dissemination of project Scientific Publications.

Each publication will be added here using the following structure:

2.5.1.1. [Title of the publication]

Publication reference and name

Publication abstract

Table 3: Title of Publication

1. Data summary	
Purpose	
Relation to the objectives of the project	
Types/Formats	
Re-use of any existing data	
Origin	
Size	
Utility for others	
2. FAIR Data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
Metadata provision	
Metadata standards	
Unique identifier	
Naming conventions	
Search keywords	

Version control	
2.2 Making data openly Accessible	
Classification	
Sharing and Access regimes	
Needed method/software	
Repository	
Access authorisation	
2.3. Making data interoperable	
Data/metadata vocabularies and other I/O standards	
Mapping to common ontologies	
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	
Licence	
Re-use availability schedule	
Re-use by third parties	
Quality assurance	
Availability period	

2.5.2. Other Publications

Other publications refer to any published material created by the consortium members during the project's lifetime that do not fall under the academic research field. Such publications may include press releases, presentations, software documentation, or produced multimedia for dissemination purposes (e.g., a FIERCE video).

All of this material will be available on the FIERCE website, either in their original form or as a link to a related social media/data repository platform (e.g., YouTube or Zenodo link) or as embedded multimedia frame (e.g., embedded radio interview). Their metadata should be available on the source.

When such material is created, special attention should be given on providing references on the various sources used. In case a source is not publicly available, consent should be required.

Publications from third parties that refer to FIERCE (e.g., a special article on a blog post or an extensive tv reportage on the FIERCE approach), or are in any other way related to FIERCE, should go through the project's Coordinator and the Dissemination leader for approval and will be also kept in a dedicated section of the FIERCE website as a reference.

3. Data Summary: Guidelines and procedures for data protection

This section details the guidelines and procedures that the entities that form part of the FIERCE Consortium are committed to following, in order to guarantee the correct protection of the sensitive data of participants.

3.1. Steps prior to data collection and data protection

Prior to the collection of any personal data, organisations must designate a Data Protection Manager whose role will be to supervise the correct processing of the personal data collected in the project. At the time of submission of the current deliverable, all project partners have identified their designated Data Protection Managers and have communicated this information internally to the whole consortium and to the project coordinator. Given the nature and dissemination level (public) of the current document, no additional information – identifiers will be provided on the Data Protection managers of each partner organisation.

In the event that the person responsible for data processing should delegate any task, such as collection, transfer or custody, he/she may appoint another person to be in charge of the processing of personal data. This person shall be committed to treating the personal data with the utmost confidentiality and discretion, exclusively for the purposes of the project, and applying all the necessary security measures to prevent access to these data by third parties. Additional information can be found in the Deliverable report D7.3

Since it is necessary to collect the explicit consent of the relevant stakeholders to participate in FIERCE activities, an Informed Consent Form has been designed and introduced in the D8.1 "OEI – Requirements No.1". The Informed Consent Form will always be subject to modifications according to the project activities and needs, translated into the relevant languages and shall at all times include the following parts:

- **Fact Sheet/Information Sheet.** It is recommended that a Fact Sheet /Information Sheet is prepared per research activity by each relevant partner. The Information Sheet should accompany the Informed Consent Form and must be ensured that the participant has understood the scope, purpose and aim of the activity, as well as in what ways it is intended that their data shall be utilized.
- **Informed Consent Form.** All participants to be given the **Informed Consent Form** and relevant information on the research activity to be completed, in a manner that is comprehensible to them prior to the activity.
- By agreeing to the Consent Form, participants provide their explicit consent for the purposes for which their data is collected, as these are listed in the Fact Sheet/Information Sheet. This document must be collected and kept by the activity leaders/partners and retained until the completion of the Project. Further guidelines on the Informed Consent Form are provided in D8.1.
- Report on Data Protection procedures implemented: Prior to the completion of the research activity, partners should ensure they keep record of a checklist for the safeguards implemented during the activity, as well as prepare a brief report on the procedures applied, for the protection of the participants' data.
- **Other, such as questionnaires.** A set of questions aimed at assessing the current situation of the relevant, targeted stakeholders. This questionnaire is necessary not only to be able to certify

the situation of the stakeholders participating in these activities, but also to receive input and evaluate the impact of the current national situation or the potential impact of the proposed actions. This document must also be collected by the organising entity, separately from the informed consent.

The Informed Consent Form and the relevant material to be disseminated to the activity participants (such as a potential questionnaire) will be linked by an anonymisation code. Thus, only the person responsible for or in charge of the data processing could link the information collected in the questionnaire with the stakeholder's identifying information. This ensures both traceability in case of an audit and anonymised processing of the information collected in the questionnaire. This facilitates the exchange of information between the partners, while for impact assessment purposes it safeguards the data protection rights of participants.

The participants' personal data collected in the Informed Consent Form may include, among others, the following: name, surname and signature, postal address, telephone number and e-mail address.

The personal data collected in the anonymised dissemination material (i.e. questionnaire) will be analysed and retained in accordance with the FIERCE Project activities and the needs as those, as these are identified under the current Work package structure. It shall always be ensured that methodologies adopted are in line with EU and national laws and regulations.

3.1.1. Methodologies for anonymization and pseudonymization as listed in FIERCE Project Deliverable D8.1:

1.1 The importance of data anonymization

In order to meet the specificities of processing personal data for scientific research purposes, Article 5(1)(e) of the GDPR indicates that *“personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for such purposes and that appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented”*. Article 89 of the GDPR adds that such measures may include anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques, provided that the intended purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, such purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.

In other words, Article 89 of the GDPR recommends “anonymisation” of data processed for research purposes. If this is not feasible, the possibility of “pseudonymisation” of data should be examined. The concepts of “anonymisation” and “pseudonymisation” are examined hereunder:

- “Anonymisation” of data means processing it with the aim of irreversibly preventing the identification of the individual to whom it relates. Data can be considered anonymised when it does not allow identification of the individuals to whom it relates, and it is not possible that any individual could be identified from the data by any further processing of that data or by processing it together with other information, which is available or likely to be available.
- “Pseudonymisation” of data means replacing any identifying characteristics of data with a pseudonym, or, in other words, a value, which does not allow the data subject to be directly identified. Pseudonymisation should be distinguished from anonymisation, as it only provides a limited protection for the identity of data subjects as it still allows identification using indirect means. Indeed, where a pseudonym is used, it is possible to identify the data subject by analyzing the underlying or related data.

For each data processing activity in which a project partner is involved as controller, this partner is committed to analyze whether anonymisation is possible to achieve the determined purpose and communicate to the Project Coordinator and relevant Task/WP Leader the anonymisation techniques that are implemented. If it is not possible to achieve the purpose with anonymised data, this partner should consider pseudonymisation and communicate to the Project Coordinator and relevant Task/WP Leader the pseudonymisation techniques that are implemented. In last resort, if the purpose cannot be fulfilled with pseudonymised data, this partner is committed to communicate to the Project Coordinator and relevant Task/WP Leader an explanation describing why the purposes cannot be achieved with anonymised or pseudonymised data.

3.1.1.1. Pseudonymization

When conducting research activities that include or may include vulnerable groups, partners must ensure that appropriate measures are taken to protect the privacy and confidentiality of research subjects. One such measure is pseudonymization, which is the process of replacing identifying information with a pseudonym or other unique identifier. This can help to minimize the risk of re-identification of research subjects while still allowing for analysis of the data.

There are several methods that may be adopted by partners to ensure pseudonymization, including:

1. Direct identifiers removal: This method involves the removal of all direct identifiers, such as names, addresses, and identification numbers, from the research data.
2. Indirect identifiers removal: This method involves the removal of any data that could indirectly identify research subjects, such as demographic data or other sensitive information.
3. Pseudonym replacement: This method involves replacing direct identifiers with a pseudonym or other unique identifier that is not linked to the subject's real identity.

Partners should ensure that appropriate pseudonymization techniques are used in compliance with relevant data protection laws and regulations, including the GDPR, in the EU. It is further provided herein the details on the pseudonymization techniques that will be used to protect the privacy and confidentiality of research subjects.

In summary, when conducting research activities that include or may include vulnerable groups, partners must ensure that appropriate measures are taken to protect the privacy and confidentiality of research subjects, and pseudonymization is one such measure that can be adopted.

For each data processing activity in which a project partner is involved as controller, they are committed to analyze whether anonymisation is possible to achieve the determined purpose and communicate to the Project Coordinator and relevant Task/WP Leader the anonymisation techniques that are implemented. If it is not possible to achieve the purpose with anonymised data, this partner should consider pseudonymisation and communicate to the Project Coordinator and relevant Task/WP Leader the pseudonymisation techniques that are implemented. In last resort, if the purpose cannot be fulfilled with pseudonymised data, this partner is committed to communicate to the Project Coordinator and relevant Task/WP Leader an explanation describing why the purposes cannot be achieved with anonymised or pseudonymised data.

3.2. Collection and protection of participants' personal data

The collection of personal data from stakeholders is foreseen to be carried out under most WPs, and definitely in WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4, before and during the participatory co-creation labs. This collection will be conducted by the project Case partners, later to be called National Labs, who before

the initiation of the relevant project activities will receive all relevant templates and protocols to be followed along with a training on data protection provided by the Data Protection Officers of the partners and (if deemed necessary) the Ethics Advisor, in alignment with the deliverables and training plan of the Project.

With the delivery of trainings, it will be ensured that the partners will be fully informed and aligned with the procedures prescribed in the Data Management Plan of the project. It shall further be safeguarded that at the beginning of each activity in which human participants will be involved, participants will have the opportunity to be informed, in a clear and simple manner of the elements of the activity, the purpose for collection of their personal data and the methods applied for its protection.

If applicable, this information would also be given to legal representatives or guardians. More specifically:

- **Consent shall be formally requested in writing from all persons participating in the activities (via the submission of an Informed Consent Form and/or provision of the same via email, verbal confirmation with an element of proof to be retained by the partners).**

It shall be ensured that participants have the reasoning to voluntarily and freely participate in the activities.

Participants will be informed that their participation is voluntary, voluntary and free of charge, and that they may withdraw at any time, with the consequent and immediate removal of all their records generated up to that point.

Ensure that participants have sufficient information about the FIERCE project, its objectives, planned activities and procedures for withdrawing their consent, and allow sufficient time to resolve any doubts that may arise.

Confidentiality and anonymity will be respected, and the identity of the participants will not be revealed without their explicit consent.

All the data collected through the questionnaire is anonymised at the time it is completed, together with the Informed Consent Form. In order for this anonymisation to be effective, and after completing the Informed Consent Form.

Analysis of Data: The analysis data is to be sent to the Project Coordinator and the Ethics Advisor only (no other members will be in copy), via email, in the form of an Excel spreadsheet. It is not to be uploaded directly onto the project repository. The Coordinator and Ethics Advisor can make two copies of the data document. One copy will remove all of the names, addresses and emails and only have a number next to the recorded observations and analyses for the participants. This document can be saved as a PDF and uploaded on the project repository to be accessible to the other partners for analysis purposes. The second document will only have the names/addresses and the Excel numbers of the participants, also saved as a PDF. This document (the data key) will be stored, by the Project Coordinator and the Ethics Advisor, outside of the computer (USB stick kept apart from any laptop or computer). The photos and videos can follow the same process (as recorded data) – there will be no names associated with the images or recordings but stored separately on the data key.

Although the collection of personal data on paper is foreseen, it is envisaged that some organisations may decide to collect these data digitally, either during, prior to or after the development of the

activities. To this end, entities must use software that guarantees data protection throughout the entire cycle, from collection to custody.

3.2.1. Activities that require data collection

Some of the main Project activities that will involve data collection include the:

- (i) national labs & transnational meetings labs;
- (ii) focus groups;
- (iii) interviews; and
- (iv) summer schools.

The implementation of the activities described above will have as one of their main elements the collection of different types of data, such as names, addresses, email or social media contacts and further sensitive data including personal views, sexual orientation, opinions, images and voice or video recordings.

As a result, the activities that the present document will encompass are related to the tasks described in the FIERCE DOA while are also required to refer to this Deliverable as well as to all Deliverable reports of WP7 and WP8 to ensure that they are following the principles prescribed in relation to data privacy, protection and ethical guidelines.

3.3. Management and custody of the collected data

It is foreseen that personal data from stakeholders will be collected on paper. From the set of data provided by the participants, special attention should be given to the informed consent. This not only ensures that participants have given their explicit consent to participate in the activities, but also contains the personal data allowing the identification of the participants.

Since all this information will be on paper, it is the responsibility of each FIERCE Data Protection Manager, or the person he/she delegated, to store and safeguard this information in a secure place. This should be a locked place to which only the person responsible for the data protection has access.

If the original documents are transcribed into a digital file, this shall be stored on a secure server, in a password-protected area, to which only the person in charge of data protection shall have access. If stored on a removable drive, this shall be protected by a password of more than 8 digits.

The originals and all copies shall be treated in the same way as regards the protection of the confidentiality and integrity of the originals. The originals will have to be stored until the personal data are destroyed.

Only anonymised information collected in the questionnaires may be shared with the Consortium entities. This anonymisation will contain letters and numbers and cannot be sequential. The data collected in the activities covered by the FIERCE project will only be used for the specific purposes of the project.

When personal data are to be destroyed, they shall follow the following protocols:

In the case of a paper-based format, the documents shall be shredded.

In case of digital media allowing overwriting (cloud servers, hard disks, USB sticks, etc.), it shall be formatted or overwritten at least twice.

In case of digital media which do not allow overwriting (CD-R, DVD-R, etc.), the media shall be destroyed by shredding or similar.

These measures will be continuously monitored during the collection, transport, storage and destruction of data by each FIERCE Data Protection Manager in order to prevent information leakage.

3.4. Open access to research data

The FIERCE project voluntarily signs up for the "Open Research Data Pilot". This means that at least all data collected in FIERCE and needed to validate the results included in scientific publications should be made open. However, this is subject to the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". In other words, access to certain data may be limited if there is a reasonable justification.

In this case, access to participants' personal data is limited from the very beginning in order to comply with the GDPR. Access to this information may not be provided to any entity under any circumstances, and its processing by the entity in charge of its protection will always be in line with the objectives of the FIERCE project, as well as the EU and national laws and regulations.

For the information collected in surveys, open access will be provided to anonymised data exclusively used in scientific publications. This information will be included together with the publications or, alternatively, will be provided through an existing, internationally recognised open data repository, such as Zenodo.

Academic or research papers published in connection with the FIERCE project will be made openly available for free access by the entire community. Priority will be given to publication in Open Access journals and publishers, or alternatively, in those that offer a Gold Open Access article processing charge (APC). In the event that it is not possible to publish the original article in open access, open access will be provided to the pre-print of the document, storing it in one or more open repositories, and where the reference to the original article will be indicated.

4. Ethical Considerations

The main ethical considerations of the FIERCE project and its data are related to privacy. The FIERCE consortium is aware of potential ethical, fundamental rights, privacy and data protection implications that may be identified in the course of the project, and the consortium is fully committed to adhering to and promote the highest ethical, fundamental rights and legal standards, as recognized at the European Union and International level, in the project's activities and outcomes.

Sensitive information might be revealed about democratic and gender discriminatory practices and behaviours at the involved organisations/national laboratories/local participants and acknowledges that in the unfortunate event of such leakage of such information, there may be negative, but still mitigatable consequences to the participating parties. **Therefore, keeping all involved parties safe is a priority and all collected personal data will be anonymized and kept confidential and encrypted.**

The FIERCE consortium ensures that the project's research ethics comply with relevant national and EU legislation, regardless of the country where the research is carried out.

The following deliverables analyse the Ethical Aspects in more detail:

- **D7.1 - Project Handbook and Management Plan** (M3)
- **D7.2 – Data Management Plan** – (M6)
- **D8.1 OEI – Requirement No. 1** (M3)
- **D8.1 OEI – Requirement No. 3** (*To be delivered*) (M12)

4.1.1. Project Work break structure and proactive approach

Each partner is responsible for following the European as well as the national legislation concerning the protection of personal data and the involvement of humans in social scientific research. In addition to, the project's overall management structure, the WP and task leaders will further secure in a proactive manner through guidance and internal checks that partners involved in the collection, handling and processing of personal data ensure the anonymity of human participants.

5. Ethics Approvals per Partner

Due to the fact that the FIERCE Project includes human participants in a number of information-gathering activities such as interviews, workshops, and focus groups, it is essential that Ethical Approvals per Partner are obtained prior to the commencement of activities.

Ethical research is honest, rigorous, transparent, and respectful and protects participants. Participants are a valuable part of the research process and not merely a means of accessing data. The ethical review provides protection for participants and also helps to protect the researcher.

By obtaining Ethical Approval, partners demonstrate that they have adhered to the accepted ethical standards of a genuine research study. Participants have the right to know who has access to their data and what is being done with it. If Ethical Approval has not been obtained, the individual researcher bears personal responsibility for any claims that may be made.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that many publishers will not accept for publication results of research that was not ethically approved.

Therefore, it is recommended that in D8.3. (due in M12, Sensitive in terms of dissemination status) copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans obtained by all partners and will be attached to the deliverable.

The opinions/approvals should address the research, which includes participants for all activities.

As a result, and in order to comply with Ethical Requirements, before the commencement of each research activity involving human participants, each beneficiary must obtain:

- (a) An Ethics Committee Approval/Opinion. If there is no proper structure to provide authorisations/approvals in the institution performing research involving participants, based on the principle of proportionality and according to practice, an ethics opinion may be given, for example, by: the University committee of the co-ordinator, the University committee of another research partner, approval from a relevant authority in the country (if applicable), ethics review by the European Commission. In FIERCE, if there is no proper structure to provide authorisations/approvals in the institution performing research involving participants, the Ethics Advisor may be declared as competent. The Ethics Approvals are to be obtained **once (one-off approval)** for each partner and should capture all relevant activities they will undertake over the course of the Project.
- (b) Any notification or authorisation for activities raising ethical issues required under national and/or European law needed for implementing the action tasks in question.

Before conducting an activity involving human participants, each Partner must carefully describe this activity, obtain the above-mentioned opinion/notification or authorisation and transmit these documents to the Project Coordinator. If these documents are not in English, they must be submitted together with an English summary, which shows that the action tasks in question are covered and includes the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned (if available).

The table hereunder suggests the possible format followed / checked by the Project Coordinator and all partners in conducting research activities involving the participation of humans, identifying such activities and the ethical opinions and or approvals that are required.

A sample of an Ethics Committee clearance is included in D7.3

Table 1: Ethical Approvals per Partner

Partner Name	Research activity involving humans	Opinions/Approvals by Ethics Committees and/or competent authorities	Ethical Approval Provided [Y/N] & relevant comments
<i>Example: Aalborg Universitet</i>	<i>Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders</i>	<i>Ethical Committee of Denmark / Ethical Committee of the Organisation led by [NAME], [EMAIL]</i>	<i>Y – Full approval</i>

In addition to the above procedures, the approvals received by the internal committees and the different procedures set out by the involved organisations and institutions for the ethical conduct of all project activities, in full line with the GDPR and the relevant directives and regulations and in parallel to the safety nets foreseen, the FIERCE Consortium will secure the ethical conduct of activities as well as the protection of human participants also via the tools and mechanisms that are in place under the overall project management structure. The Work Package Structure, with the partners leading the relevant Work packages along with the constant support of the Project Coordinators, the Scientific Coordinators and the Ethics Advisor, (who will support the project partners and the project activities throughout the project implementation period), securing this way the ethical conduct of all project activities.

6. Summary and Conclusions

The present deliverable attempts an early approach to the definition of the FIERCE DMP. Described are the main principles and regulations which the DMP is aligned with, as well as the methodology deriving thereof. Following the EU guidelines regarding open access to scientific publications and research data, and FAIR Data Management, partners are prompted to use consistently the adapted FAIR Data template for presentation of all expected data. Such data is categorised in four main groups: public deliverables, software components, research datasets and publications. The relevant storage solutions are set out in a dedicated section along with the characteristics that made them an appropriate choice. In the light of the changes in EU data protection regulation, identification of the GDPR roles (controllers, processors, recipients) even among the consortium partners is crucial for clarifying data protection responsibilities. Personal data that will be acquired for the FIERCE needs and the relevant data processing activities is, to the extent possible, foreseen and described.

All the above-mentioned approaches and methodology will mainly serve as a guideline for handling the data that will stem from the project. As stated before, this document is intended to be a living document; the presented version of the DMP herein is not final and remains subject to adjustments, modifications and amendments over the course of the project, as may be required. A final version of the DMP will be included at the end of the project [M36], as part of WP7, (as well as in project month 24 under D7.4), where all data that is generated and processed during the project will be presented, along with a data management and dissemination plan to be applied post-completion of the project.

I.1 FAIR Template

The FAIR Template is presented in the following table. Details on the content of the table can be found in the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020⁷.

Table: Annex I - 1 H2020 FAIR DMP Template

DMP component	Issues to be addressed
1. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State the purpose of the data collection/generation • Explain the relation to the objectives of the project • Specify the types and formats of data generated/ collected • Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any) • Specify the origin of the data • State the expected size of the data (if known) • Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful
2. FAIR Data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision) • Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers, URL etc.? • Outline naming conventions used • Outline the approach towards search keyword • Outline the approach for clear versioning • Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what type of metadata will be created and how
2.2 Making data openly Accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so • Specify how the data will be made available • Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? • Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited • Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions
2.3. Making data interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. • Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

DMP component	Issues to be addressed
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify how the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why Describe data quality assurance processes Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable
3. Allocation of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation
4. Data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
5. Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
6. Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refer to other national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

I.2 Adapted FAIR template

Below is the Adapted FAIR Template, as modified for the purpose of describing the FIERCE project datasets/modules.

Table: Annex II - 2 Adapted FAIR Template

1. Data summary	
Purpose	
Relation to the objectives of the project	
Types/Formats	
Re-use of any existing data	
Origin	
Size	
Utility for others	
2. FAIR Data	
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	

Metadata provision	
Metadata standards	
Unique identifier	
Naming conventions	
Search keywords	
Version control	
2.2 Making data openly Accessible	
Classification	
Sharing and access regimes	
Needed method/software	
Repository	
Access authorisation	
2.3. Making data interoperable	
Data/metadata vocabularies and other I/O standards	
Mapping to common ontologies	
2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	
Licence	
Re-use availability schedule	
Re-use by third parties	
Quality assurance	
Availability period	

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